

Tiwah (Funeral Ritual of Southern Borneo/Kalimantan)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Syncretic Religions, Southeast Asian Religions, Language, Austronesian, Greater Barito linkage, Maanyan-Paku, Ngaju, Lawangan, Ot Danum, Siang, Folk Religion, Southeast Asian Syncretisms, Kaharingan, Kaharingan

The Tiwah was a central ritual among the amalgam of traditional beliefs and spiritualities of southern Borneo/Kalimantan. The ritual varies by period and region, but almost always involved the unearthing and reburial of remains of the deceased that symbolized one's leaving of the current world to another, as well as the erection of a Sandung shrine/coffin. This treatment of the bones are central to the spiritual well being of the family of the deceased, whereas the communal dancing and feasting of the Tiwah are also important for maintaining the cohesion and happiness of the village community. The Tiwah is led by religious/spiritual experts, known as Basir/Balian. The bulk of this entry is based on historical sources and treatises. The author has also been on field work several times to Borneo, with two extended field trips to Central Kalimantan. Field observations, together with interviews with descendants of religious practitioners, offer equally if not more substantial corroboration to the textual sources. Still, given the immense diversity of Tiwah practices across geographical and chronological breadths, a conclusive reduction of its essence remains difficult. Criticisms and augments are extremely welcome.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2000 CE

Region: Central Kalimantan

Region tags: Indonesia, Asia, Southeast Asia, Borneo

Central Kalimantan is an Indonesian province. It was created in 1957, out of a division of South Kalimantan, in an effort to give Dayak people greater sovereignty. Palangkaraya, the capital, was created in a three year construction project. The population of Central Kalimantan is only a plural majority Dayak, however (46%), with Javanese (22%) also making up a significant minority of the population. Islam is the majority religion (about 75% of the population), yet it is also this region that the small Kaharingan community considers home.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

↳ Enclosed?

– No

↳ Elevated?

– No

↳ By a body of water?

– Yes

Notes: Access to river is ubiquitous to all Dayak villages. The Tiwah being a village-based event, is no exception.

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: The burial grounds, the Sandung shrines, and the temporarily erected and decorated Tiwah poles are all spiritual spaces in Central Kalimantan Dayak lives. The ritual also involves spiritual and symbolic holy spaces, i.e. the upper world and under world, where ancestral spirits (Sangiang/ Nyaring) live. Traditionally, the word "Tajahan" denotes the sacred site where Tiwah is to be held.

Reference: Schärer, Hans. Ngaju Religion. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.23

↳ Other [Specify]

– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– No

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Notes: In olden days, there seem to be a highly hierarchical division of labor in the spiritual work of Tiwah, with the bone-cleaning, musical performance, and spiritual works mostly done by a class of lower-caste, otherwise usually shunned, almost enslaved people who were also considered spiritually potent (according to works by Mallinckrodt and Schaerer). Nowadays, this kind of discrimination is less observable, and often times it is the immediate family of the deceased that performed the traditionally "dirty" work reserved for the lower-class professionals.

Reference: Schärer, Hans. Ngaju Religion. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.50-55

Reference: Mallinckrodt, Jacob. Het Adatrecht Van Borneo, Deel 1. Leiden: M, Dubbeldeman, 1927.

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: The Tiwah is a public event where entire communities are invited and encouraged to take part in. However, the most essential kernel among all its rituals take part in the private burial grounds of a family, where the coffin (often a Banama/life-boat-shaped one) gets elevated, opened, and the bones of the deceased are to be reburied in the family's private Sandung shrine. Therefore, there is an element of opening a family's very private spaces temporarily to the public.

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Tiwah is held in the village commons. Access to waterways is usually necessary, as the arrival and passing of spiritual workers are often by the means of boats.

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: The site becomes sacred during the ritual. Erection of the imitation life tree (Batang Garing) in the form of a cluster of poles is a particularly religious action, and once it is done, the space around it attains a temporarily sacred, liminal status.

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

Notes: The shack for percussion music band (Balai Tiwah), the memorial pole (Tiang Pantar), and the circle of thin poles (Sangkaraya) serving as the centerpiece of dancing, sacrificial killing, and other festivities are all constructed on the spot or temporarily requisited.

↳ Was it temporary?

– Yes

Notes: The sites of the public festivities are temporary. Erecting and decorating the Balai building and the festivity centerpiece, the Sangkaraya, are in fact central to the ceremonies. The cemetery and the Sandung shrine/ossuary, where the bones of the deceased are transferred between, are permanent.

↳ Was it permanent?

– No

Notes: Only the Sandung shrine/ossuary is permanent. In the Siang land of upper/middle Barito, totem poles after each Tiwah is also left to remain as a token of memorial.

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: The sites of the Tiwah are multiple. Many of these sites are integral to the Ngaju cosmology. The boat that carry the spiritual mediums (Basir), the boat- and hornbill-shaped coffin, and the stilted Sandung shrine/ossuary, all serve as means of transportation and transcendence for the soul of the deceased between the upper, under, and human worlds.

Reference: Schärer, Hans. Ngaju Religion. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.p. 51-53

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– No

Notes: While the sites of the Tiwah do function as mediums between metaphysical spaces, they tend not to embody such sites directly.

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– I Don't Know

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The sites, if oriented to any spatial features, should at least align with water bodies. There should be adequate access to the river to allow the boat carrying the spiritual medium (Basir/Balian) to dock on arrival, but high enough for the land to be dry and firm. The site should be far away from any forests that potentially contain spiritual pollutants to the rituals. Since the rituals are held within village spaces, they also follow the general rules of village positioning in Dayak social life.

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– I Don't Know

Notes: The ritual is performed less and less frequent throughout the 20th century and the 21st century, as Dayaks convert to Christianity and Islam.

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 84

Notes: The Tiwah takes place over several days, the number of which is determined by 1) the economic capacity of the family hosting the reburial, and by 2) mandate of the head Basir (spiritual medium) holding

the event. 84 hours, or 7 days, is usually a maximum for common families. In the late 19th century, some feudal lords could manage week after week of Tiwah rituals, which could be even more eclectic in style than the modern, barebone ones discussed here.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Reference: Schiller, Anne. "Talking Heads: Capturing Dayak Deathways on Film" 28, no. 1 (February 2001). <https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.2001.28.1.32>.

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 3

Notes: There are usually at least 3 spiritual mediums present at the Tiwah, often more. The number is always an odd one.

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they male:

– Yes

Notes: The Basir (spiritual medium) are usually male.

↳ Are they female:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the spiritual medium (Balian) are predominantly female and non-binary. Do note that the title "Balian" carry very different meanings all over Borneo, as the Iban, Taman, Tawoyan, and Meratus peoples all use it albeit for different spiritual roles. In other parts of Indonesia the word also sees wide usage.

Reference: Tsing, Anna. *In the Realm of the Diamond Queen*. Princeton University Press, 1993.

↳ Are they transgender:

– I Don't Know

Notes: The non-binary Balian is discussed below.

↳ Are they non-binary:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally Balian could be gender non-binary individuals from a special class of Dayaks (at least among the Ngaju) trained in the Sangiang language and other techniques.

↳ Are they other:

– I Don't Know

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– N/A

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– No

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: Before slavery was officially abolished in the Ngaju-speaking regions in 1894, the Balian and Basirs were often times enslaved people purchased for these particular professions. Even after, they tended to be staffed by the freed ex-slaves or lower castes of society (according to Schaer's observation). As mentioned, the profession once connoted prostituting oneself. Nowadays, this discrimination does not seem to hold any more, at least overtly. The head priest of Kaharingan in Central Kalimantan (the "Damang") in fact holds considerable political power, especially after the Reformasi.

Reference: Schärer, Hans. Ngaju Religion. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.p. 42-43

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– Yes

Notes: In the past, Balian and Basir were initiated when they were very young.

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

Notes: The Balian and Basir once had their own community, ostracized from the "normal" or "mundane" Dayaks to a certain extent due to their lower social class but also fearsome powers. They were thus simultaneously insiders and outsiders.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: See previous entry.

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: See previous answers.

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Social caste: See previous answers.

– Religious affiliation or status: The Balian/Basir statuses have always been considered mutually

exclusive with Abrahamic religions. Participating in Tiwah, however, is most usually tolerated or at least considered in the grey area by the latter.

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Tiwah is essentially an attempt of communication and deliverance of the deceased soul to their community of ancestors. The ancestral spirits (Liau) dwelling in Dayak upper world is therefore the most essential participant or agent in the ritual. The high god (Ranying Hatalla Langit) and other divine beings (Nyaring, etc) are lesser participants in the Tiwah.

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: There is usually a large entourage of performers and service providers at Tiwah, as well as an even larger crowd of guests/spectators.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:
– I Don't Know

↳ Non-binary:
– I Don't Know

↳ Other:
– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?
– N/A

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?
– No

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– No

Notes: See previous section on "agents". There are different degrees to which supernatural beings take parts in the rituals.

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Notes: Tiwah often reaches inter-village scale. The number of spectators vary. In the heyday of Dayak spiritualism (late 19th century) it could easily exceed a thousand for Tiwaha of important chiefs. Today it is also common to have more than a hundred.

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– I Don't Know

↳ Non-binary:

– Yes

Notes: As with the "agent" of the rituals, spectators of the Tiwah would also include spiritual-working individuals (sangiang) considered outlying of traditional gender binary.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?

– N/A

↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The number and extent of invitations for the Tiwah ritual largely speak for the grandeur and glory attained by the hosts of the event. They also often contribute labor and ambiance to the overall experience

↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: Cleansing, oiling, and transferring to Sandung of the bones of the deceased is strictly limited to the family and professionals. Spectators are usually not allowed to perform the sacrificial killing of animals.

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The chanting, music, and animal sacrifices in Tiwah are all meant to intensify communication with the supernatural world, where a great number of spiritual beings' attention are drawn. They include not just the high god, but also lesser gods or specters such as the ancestral souls Liau, the wind and thunder god Nyaro, the forest evil gods Nyaring, and so on.

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: The Sangiang (ancestors transforming into higher beings) are thought to be watching the village at all times, and Tiwah is meant to restore calm between the Sangiang and human worlds after the deceased soul created imbalance between the two.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– I Don't Know

Notes: The high god, "Ranying Hatalla", is among the gods that spectate the Tiwah and awaits the soul of the deceased subject to Tiwah.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Others:

– I Don't Know

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– No

Notes: The most critical determinant for a Tiwah to be held is its host's economic preparedness. Equally important is the choosing of an auspicious day not in conflict with the cultural taboo dates, usually a choice made by the head Basir. The availability of musicians and Basirs are also essential factors.

Is participation obligatory?

– No

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– No

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– No

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– Yes

Notes: The Ngaju spiritual workers have a system of taboos (pali/pamali) to determine favorable and unfavorable days.

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death,

etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is most closely associated with the deaths of important individuals, and sometimes, important deaths (the ones that are particularly abnormal and warranting redressing of spiritual balance).

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: While omens are not direct causes for Tiwah, those that take place during the deaths of the deceased, as well as those that take place during the corpses' first burial, could be partially addressed in the Tiwah itself.

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– Yes

↳ Does this ritual take place to aid conception?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place immediately postpartum?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place during a marriage?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place during pregnancy?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place during the coming of age period?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place at the time of entrance to the religious group?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place in preparation for death?

– No

↳ Does this ritual take place after death?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced during other social status changes?

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Notes: The Tiwah is always sponsored by the family of the deceased, and getting economically prepared for the Tiwah has become essential to the ritual itself.

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: Holders of Tiwah seek to address the imbalance and uneasiness in the spiritual sense caused by deaths, especially tumultuous ones. In such a way Tiwah could be seen as a means which maintains the spiritual well being of a community. For instance, giving a proper Tiwah to one's deceased spouse is the expected prerequisite for a widow/widower to remarry, as the Tiwah serves a pacifying, neutralizing purpose in the community.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– No

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: See above in "maintenance".

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– No

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

Notes: In Tiwah there is the element of purifying the deceased one's bones by both physical cleansing, oiling with fragrant oils, and by recitals of Sangiang mantras to spiritually prepare the deceased for their ascendance to a more elevated world.

↳ Is it mental:

– Yes

Notes: See entry above.

↳ Is it emotional:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– No

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– No

Notes: As discussed in entry on "maintenance" purposes of the ritual, the Tiwah addresses a state of general spiritual imbalance in the community induced by one's passing away. A more direct consequence of such imbalance is the assumed uneasiness among the collective ancestral spirits (liau) of the village and especially the deceased one's family. This in turn could be used to interpret dissatisfaction in crop yields, market prices, etc. Therefore, the ritual of Tiwah is indeed linked to maintenance of the community's modes of subsistence, but in a fairly indirect way.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– No

Notes: Again, as mentioned in entries on "maintenance" and "subsistence", Tiwah is more about the keeping of order and balance than a specific act of protection, even though the effect could be interpreted as protecting the community from potential harms by the ancestral spirits in the case

that Tiwah is failed to be carried out.

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– Yes

Notes: Tiwah is deeply associated with the travel of the deceased soul by means of a spiritual ship (banama) from the underworld to the upperworld, uniting with the collective of ancestral spirits, which reside together with the high god Ranying Hatalla. This orthodox Ngaju narrative is, of course, less pertinent in adjacent areas that celebrate Tiwah, such as among the Siang-Murung people.

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– No

Notes: The ritual indirectly coheres the community as guests interact with each other, but at its kernel Tiwah remains an interaction between the deceased and their immediate family.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– I Don't Know

Notes: The author has not encountered an incidence of Tiwah where the outcome was deemed undesirable or inauspicious.

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: At the Tiwah, the key instrument is Garantung (percussion gongs like those played in Gamelan). A band of them usually accompany the entire festivity, especially the dances around the Sangkaraya.

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– I Don't Know

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– No

Notes: There is usually a chant by the Basir in key moments of Tiwah (removal of bones, erection of bones to Sandung, sacrifices, etc.). But these chants are usually not synchronized with the Garantung's rhythm.

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– No

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Garantung is a set of gongs hung in a designated music shack, meant to be performed at the highlight moments of the Tiwah.

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums,

cylindrical drums).

– No

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– No

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– Yes

Notes: The shack housing the Garantung, while simple, is essential.

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: Usually less than 10.

↳ Is it scripted?

– Yes

Notes: There are chants memorized and recited by spiritual mediums (Basir) at key moments of the Tiwah. They utilize spiritual languages unbeknownst to common folks (bahasa sangiang).

↳ Is it semantic?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

↳ Does it require formal training?

– Yes

Notes: The Basir (and traditionally, also the gender-non-conformative Balian) spiritual mediums used to be highly specifically trained by their parents, slave-owners, or teachers. Today they are sometimes only doing it part-time while working a day job.

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– No

Notes: The Garatung music does not have much variety throughout the Tiwah.

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– I Don't Know

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– Yes

Notes: The Garantung, just like most percussion music in the Indonesian Archipelago, have highly codified patterns.

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: One could refer to this video for the rhythm:

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dTS5LNtd34g&list=RDdTS5LNtd34g&start_radio=1)

[v=dTS5LNtd34g&list=RDdTS5LNtd34g&start_radio=1](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dTS5LNtd34g&list=RDdTS5LNtd34g&start_radio=1)

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Fixed

Notes: The styles of the Garantung seem to be fairly stable within each cultural zones of the Ngaju, (Kahayan, Kapuas, Katingan, and Seruyan) but do vary across them. The non-Ngaju Dayaks who also practice Tiwah, eg. Ot Danum and Siang-Murung, have their own varieties of music much removed from the Garantung described here.

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: In Ngaju

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

Notes: The Ganrantung music of the Ngaju (and other percussion music of adjacent Dayak groups) are highly rhythmic, and serve as basic guidance for dance movements.

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– No

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– N/A

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Besides the Basirs/Balian, who don their highly decorated celebratory dresses, usual attenders and the family of the deceased usually do not have to dress specifically for the Tiwah.

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The head basir sometimes dons a conical hat (woven bamboo and rattan) decorated with bird feathers. See also Schaerer, *Ngaju Religion*, Figure 11-13, pp. 135-6

↳ Is it removed at some point during the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it added during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: See "head covering".

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– No

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

Reference: Schärer, Hans. Ngaju Religion. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.23-24, 64-65

↳ Are they totems:

– No

Notes: The "Sangkaraya" poles (symbolizing the tree of life "Batang Garing") and the "Hampatung" figures (symbolizing the soul of the deceased) are often regarded as "totem" but the author finds the allegory to be not particularly meaningful.

↳ Are they religious icons:

– No

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

↳ Are they vessels:

– Yes

Notes: The Sanggaran could be interpreted as a vessel that bears the communication between the upper and under worlds. (See Schärer)

↳ Are they masks:

– No

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– Yes

Notes: The Sanggaran is decorated with colorful flags.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– Yes

Notes: The Tiwah decorations, especially the Sangkaraya, are erected in the days leading to the Tiwah. They act as a centerpiece during the event.

↳ Are they sound-producing:

– No

↳ Are they divination tools:

– No

↳ Are they drug paraphenalia:

– No

↳ Are they cutting devices:

– No

↳ Are they sceptres/wands:

– No

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it a diagram:

– No

↳ Is it an inscribed item:

– No

↳ Is it a book:

– Yes

Notes: The author has come across printed chant books in his field work. The texts, in Sangiang language unintelligible to commoners, are chanted and sung at the Tiwah.

↳ Is it a scroll:

– No

↳ Is it a tablet:

– No

↳ Is it memorized text:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: See "Offering".

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: A significant part of Tiwah is the purification and sanctification of unearthed human remains.

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is water used?

– No

↳ Is earth used?

– No

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

↳ Are textiles used?

– No

↳ Is fire used?

– No

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Sanggaran is not touched or altered. Rather, it serves as a centerpiece to orient dances and sacrifice moves, which happen around the Sanggaran.

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– No

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– No

↳ Is it used to touch?

– No

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– No

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– Yes

Notes: During the Tiwah, the Sanggaran is indeed considered a holy object not to be tempered with.

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

Notes: Buffaloes, pigs, and chickens are the most consumed.

↳ Is it a plant:

– No

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– No

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

Notes: Killing of the animals, especially buffaloes, are highly ritualized.

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– No

Notes: Presentation of the meats is not particularly ritualized.

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– No

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– No

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– No

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– No

- ↳ Does food consumption happen on site?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?
 - No

- ↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?
 - No

- ↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?
 - No

- ↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?
 - No

- ↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?
 - No

- ↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?
 - No

- ↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it a type of alcoholic drink?
 - Yes

↳ Is it naturally fermented:

– Yes

Notes: A fermented rice Tuak is often consumed at Tiwah by both the spiritual practitioners and the attendants.

↳ Is it distilled:

– No

↳ Is it a stimulant?

– No

↳ Does it contain cacao?

– No

↳ Does it contain kava?

– No

↳ Is it cannabis or cannabinoid?

– No

↳ Is it opium?

– No

↳ Is it MDMA?

– No

↳ Is it a psychedelic?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoked:

– No

↳ Is it ingested:

– Yes

Notes: Tuak is consumed on its own and with food.

↳ Alone:

– Yes

↳ With food:

– Yes

↳ With liquid:

– No

↳ Is it applied topically:

– No

↳ Is it chewed:

– No

↳ Is it a suppository:

– No

↳ Is it snorted:

– No

↳ Is it injected:

– No

↳ Is it offered into the fire:

– No

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:

– No

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– No

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Notes: The famous communal jars used by the Iban people to consume rice alcohol are not attested in southern Borneo to the author's knowledge.

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Notes: The spiritual mediums (Basir/Balian), the family members, and the participants all remain in their respective stances throughout the Tiwah. The Basir and Balian merely performed the communication with ancestral spirits, without embodying or manifesting them.

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– No

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

Notes: The offerings, in the form of sacrificed animals, are cooked and consumed as food among the participants

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– No

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– No

↳ Are animals offered?

– Yes

↳ Is the whole animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many animals are offered?

– N/A

↳ Is part of the animal offered?

– No

↳ Are the animals domestic?

– Yes

↳ How many domestic?

– N/A

↳ Are they wild animals?

– No

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

Notes: Before the 1894 Tumbang Anoi conference, there were cases of human sacrifices of slaves mentioned by Mueller, Schwaner, Bock, among other western travelogues. They largely ceased to happen after 1894.

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Other cooked foods are often offered to the Sandung (some come with a platform to hold plates) alongside meat from the main sacrificial animal.

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Notes: Rice alcohol is often consumed along the food, but the author does not know if it is also part of the offering.

↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?

– No

↳ Are commodities offered?

– No

↳ Are household items offered?

– No

↳ Are personal items offered?

– No

↳ Is clothing offered?

– No

↳ Are musical instrument offered?

– No

↳ Are texts offered?

– No

↳ Are weapons offered?

– No

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– No

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is essentially the last step of a sequence of death-related proceedings in the Ngaju and adjacent Dayak cosmologies. They are still mostly standalone events, though, as no other rituals as important take place immediately before or after it.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– No

Notes: Tiwah only happens once. But its duration and ostentation vary greatly.

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– No

Notes: As above, Tiwah does not repeat.

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Notes: Anticipating the Tiwah generate excitement in the Kaharingan community not many other events could compete.

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– Low

Is there behavioral conformity?

– I Don't Know

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the roles differentiated?

– Yes

Notes: The music band demands almost extreme level of internal synchrony while playing. The participating guests, during dancing phases, are expected to dance with synchrony to a certain degree. The spiritual mediums, while chanting their more specialized mantras, would not expect non-professionals to participate in synchrony as most people do not know the words. Thus, the roles and levels of synchrony are very much differentiated.

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of entrainment?

– High

Notes: Tiwah used to be the paramount opportunity for entertainment for the inland Dayaks who otherwise would not squander resources on such a luxurious concentration of socializing, drinking, slaughtering of animals, feasting, and music.

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment emerging endogenously between participants in the ritual?

(e.g., clapping, chanting without external stimulus)

– Yes

Notes: It is often a mixture. There is group entertainment (music, dancing, community eating) but during conversations, entertainment would often emerge endogenously (individual dancing, chatting, courting, card-playing, etc.).

↳ Is the entrainment to an external stimulus?

(e.g., a ritual leader, a musical beat)

– Yes

Notes: Music is often a common external stimulus. The slaughtering of sacrificial pigs, chickens, and buffaloes are entertaining to some. In the 19th century, Balians performing transactional sexual favors was also not uncommon.

Reference: Hardeland, August. *Dajaksch-deutsches Wörterbuch*. Amsterdam: Druck von C.A. Spin & Sohn, 1859. p.p. 35

↳ Does the entrainment induce emotional conformity?

– No

Notes: The emotional effects of the Tiwah vary greatly between its participants. The immediate family of the deceased would have a much more intimate emotional investment in the event than those merely participating. Those who contribute their effort to the rituals, such as the musicians, performers, construction laborers, and spiritual mediums, would also have different levels of cultural attachments to the Tiwah as they are consciously withholding a tradition slowly falling into irrelevance.

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– Medium

Notes: The head Basir coordinates the spiritual labors and performances. His control over the guest is limited. Everyone would nevertheless still abide to the general social expectations of one at a Tiwah, that is, to respect whatever decisions made by the hosting family of the deceased.

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: As addressed in "Site" section.

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– N/A

Notes: At least one day of preparation.

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– No

↳ Does it involve purification:

– No

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– No

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– I Don't Know

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The spiritual mediums and musicians are an extremely professional force, both historically and nowadays. Training since childhood and proficiency in the Sangiang language required much dedication.

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– N/A

Notes: Tiwah is extremely costly. Building material, sacrificial animals, rental fee for boats and buildings, and most of all, wages for hiring Basirs, Balian, and musicians could amount to astronomical numbers.

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– Specify: 10+

↳ Other measure of cost:

– N/A

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Many-many

Notes: The ritual involves multiple spiritual mediums performing for both the deceased's family and large number of spectators. I thus consider it to be many-many in transmission mode.

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

– Artistic representation

– Through inspiration

Notes: See above.

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

– Sagely human

– Religious specialists

Notes: The head Basir or Balian would have the most authority over the ritual. The deceased could, however, interfere by means of their will before death. However, the rituals themselves would still have to

be conducted by the former, which constitutes a reversal of the Basir and Balian's usually lacking of political power (see section "Participants").

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tiwah (Funeral Ritual of Southern Borneo/Kalimantan), Anon. "Tiwah Footage in 1928", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bl5nzIIIDDs&t=90s>.

Reference: Tiwah (Funeral Ritual of Southern Borneo/Kalimantan), Apriyanto. "" BONGKAR MAKAM SUKU DAYAK (TIWAH TUMBANG PANGGO Part 1)""", n.d.. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sWbGV1H9g-w>.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: No, Mallinckrodt, Jacob. *Het Adatrecht Van Borneo, Deel 1*. Leiden: M, Dubbeldeman, 1927. p.548,

Reference: Yes, Schärer, Hans. *Ngaju Religion*. Springer Netherlands, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-9346-7>. p.23, p.23-24, 64-65, p.50-55, p.p. 51-53, p.p. 42-43

Reference: Yes, Schiller, Anne. "Talking Heads: Capturing Dayak Deathways on Film" 28, no. 1 (February 2001). <https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.2001.28.1.32>.

Reference: Yes, Tsing, Anna. *In the Realm of the Diamond Queen*. Princeton University Press, 1993.

Reference: Yes, Hardeland, August. *Dajaksch-deutsches Wörterbuch*. Amsterdam: Druck von C.A. Spin & Sohn, 1859. p.p. 35